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METHODS OF REDUCING THE AMOUNT OF AROMATIC HYDROCARBONS AND BENZENE IN AUTO MOBILE PETROL

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The growth of the automobile fleet and the associated increase in environmental pollution impose increasingly stringent requirements for the quality of produced gasoline in terms of their environmental properties. The review considers modern methods of reducing the content of benzene in motor gasoline to a level that meets modern environmental requirements.

Keywords: *gasoline, aromatic hydrocarbons, benzene, hydrogenation, hydroisomerization, alkylation, extraction, reforming*

The main goal of maintaining the environmental security of the country is to "provide the environment at a high level in order to improve the health and living conditions of the population."

Motor transport is one of the main factors that have a relatively harmful effect on the health of the population and the protection of nature. Environmental problems of transport can be achieved through the protection and development of

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the environment. Improvement of the country's environmental systems, in particular compliance with international environmental requirements for fuel and toxic gases emitted by motor vehicles, will have a positive effect on the environment.

There are the following main reasons for the negative impact of the transport industry on the environment [1-3]:

- lack of a specific environmental goal in the production of motor vehicles and its development sectors;
- low ecological properties of manufactured motor vehicles;
- failure to improve the quality of fuel products;
- low quality of roads.

Motor transport is a powerful environmental pollutant, causing noise in cities and increased environmental heat. Every year in the world, 26 mln. more than tons of toxic gases containing carcinogenic substances are released [4].

In order to eliminate the above-mentioned problems and improve the environment, it is necessary to carry out extensive scientific research in two directions and to apply them in practice: first, to improve the environmental properties of motor fuels; and secondly, improvement of IYON of motor vehicles.

The sharp increase in demand for oil and gas products is causing various serious environmental problems in the world. Taking this into account, the Republic of Uzbekistan pays great attention to improving the quality of oil products and producing environmentally friendly oil products based on local raw materials and technologies.

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Table 1

Modern requirements for gasoline quality

Indicators	Requirements		
	Euro-3	Euro-4	Euro-5
Benzene content , %	1.0	1 , 0	1.0
Sulfur content , %	0.015	0.005	0.001
Amount of aromatic hydrocarbons , %	42	35	35
Amount of olefinic hydrocarbons , %	18	14	14
Oxygen content , %	2.3	2.7	2.7
Fractional composition , %:			
Saturated vapor pressure , kPa	summer 70 winter 90	summer 70 winter 90	summer 70 winter 90

In the first direction, the fuel industry in our country is making the transition to the requirements of European standards (Euro-3, Euro-4, Euro-5) on anti-detonation and environmental properties of gasoline and diesel fuel (Table 1) [5].

In the second direction, it requires increasing the environmental safety of domestically produced and imported vehicles. In this direction, as of July 1, 2016, the "Euro-5" environmental requirement was developed in Europe (Table 2) [6].

Table 2

Technical norms of Euro 1-5 environmental standards

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Standard	Carbon dioxide (II) CO	Hydrocarbon	Volatility of organic substances	Nitrous oxide (NO _x)	HC+ NOX	Suspended Particles (RM)
Euro-1	2.72 (3.16)	-	-	-	0.97 (1.13)	-
Euro-2	2, 2	-	-	-	0, 5	-
Euro-3	2.3	0.20	-	0.15	-	-
Euro-4	1.0	0.10	-	0.08	-	-
Euro-5	1,000	0.100	0.68	0.060	-	0.005

In these areas, scientific research is being carried out on a large scale in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The main goal of our scientific research is focused on the first direction, i.e. improving the environmental properties of motor fuels, especially gasoline. Therefore, we studied the physical and chemical properties of local low-octane gasoline, and as a result of the research, it was found that the content of aromatic hydrocarbons, especially benzene, in the composition of local gasoline is unusually high. Based on the results of this research, the following are modern methods of reducing the content of aromatic hydrocarbons, especially benzene, in gasoline.

Analyzing the local reforming process, there are two main ways to reduce the content of aromatic hydrocarbons, especially benzene, in gasoline:

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- pre-reforming fractionation, that is, separation of benzene-forming components from the raw materials included in the reforming process. This increases the initial boiling temperature of gasoline to 95-100 °C.

- fractionation after reforming. In this case, a certain part of aromatic hydrocarbons is separated from the reformat composition and processed.

Fractionation before reforming. The research results of [7, 8] show that when the initial boiling temperature of reforming raw materials is increased from 85 to 110 °C, the amount of benzene in the reformat content decreases from 4.3 to 1.2%.

Reforming unit calculations and analysis have shown that benzene is produced by dealkylation of heavy aromatic hydrocarbons, not by its constituents. When the initial temperature of the raw material of the agar reforming process is increased, the formation of benzene in the reformat will increase due to the dealkylation of aromatic hydrocarbons. Dealkylation of highly aromatic hydrocarbons increases with increasing temperature and pressure of the reforming process [9].

Thus, the possibilities of the fractionation process of the reforming feedstock before reforming to reduce the content of benzene in the reformat are relatively limited. In addition, when using this method, the reforming process leads to a decrease in raw material resources, aggravation of the fractional composition of the reformat, and the formation of boiling fractions in the temperature range of more than 70-105 (110) °C. Due to the significant amount of this fraction (25-30% of the boiling fraction in the temperature range of 70-180 °C) and its low octane number (60 and

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below), it is not possible to add it to commercial gasoline. "VNIINeftekhim" developed a process of hydroisomerization in order to increase the octane number of the boiling fraction in the temperature range of 70-105 °C [10]. The process is carried out in the usual hydroisomerization scheme with the participation of the GIP-06 catalyst, at a temperature of 170-250 °C and under a pressure of 2.5-3.5 MPa and with the help of a gas containing 600-800 nm³/m³ of hydrogen. As a result, the octane number of this fraction increases by 10-14 points and is 72 on average. By introducing such devices in oil refineries (NQIZ), it will be possible to produce gasoline with less than 0.5% benzene, up to 35% aromatic hydrocarbons and 89 points in the research octane number (T.U.). In this case, the octane number T.U. For the production of 92 and higher gasolines, it is necessary to use various additives that increase the octane number.

Fractionation after reforming . There are various options for fractional reduction of the amount of aromatic hydrocarbons in the reformat after the reforming process.

One of them is the option of extracting benzene-toluene-xylene fractions from the reformat composition, and then extracting individual aromatic hydrocarbons from them [11-15]. In this case, the reformat is divided into fractions with initial boiling point (b.q.h) - 75 °C, 75-135 °C and 135 °C - final boiling point (c.q.h), of which 75-135 °C In the C temperature range, the fraction is directed to an individual aromatic hydrocarbon extraction unit using the extraction method, and the remaining two fractions are used as a high-octane component for the production of automobile gasoline. For example, b.q.h. - up to 75 °C and 135 °C

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C - s.q.h. The combined octane number of the boiling fractions in the temperature range is 85.6 points in the motor method (M.U.), this component octane number is T.U. 91.3, which contains up to 4.4% less aromatic hydrocarbons and up to 3.2% less benzene compared to reformat, allows the production of automobile gasoline. The disadvantage of such devices is a sharp drop in the total production capacity of commercial gasoline in NQIZs.

Another way is to reformat b.q.h. - up to 62 °C, up to 62-105 °C and 105 °C - s.q.h. [16-17], in which the intermediate fraction is mixed with the liquid fraction from the pyrolysis process, and this mixture is then subjected to hydrotreating, selective hydrocracking and extraction processes. Then b.q.h. - 62 °C, 105 °C - s.q.h. between temperatures, boiling fractions and raffinate are compounded and commercial gasoline is produced. The disadvantages of using this technology lead to an increase in the production cost of automobile gasoline.

In another method, the benzene-containing fraction of the reformat is extracted from the reformat at temperatures between 62-85 °C and 150 °C - s.q.h. up to and separated into fractions containing S_{9+} aromatic hydrocarbons [18]. The separated fractions mixture is catalytically transalkylated benzene with C_{9+} aromatic hydrocarbons to obtain toluene and xylene fractions. Although this technology allows to significantly reduce the content of benzene in the composition of gasoline, it does not allow to reduce the total amount of aromatic hydrocarbons.

Reformat contains many methods of reducing aromatic hydrocarbons and benzene, it contains benzoic acid. It is aimed at extracting boiling fractions in the temperature range of -85 °C. The content of benzene in the rest of the reformat

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does not exceed 1%. The obtained benzene fraction can be processed using one of the following methods [7-12, 19]:

- benzene extraction;
- alkylation of benzene with olefins;
- hydrogenation of benzene to cyclohexane;
- hydroisomerization of benzene to methylcyclopentane.

valuable petrochemical product can be produced by *extracting the* benzene-containing fraction of the reformat using various solvents [102-105]. High capital and operating costs are the major barriers to the adoption of this technology.

alkylation of benzene with olefin-containing gases (ethylene, propylene, butylene) together with reducing the amount of benzene, increases the octane number by T.U. It allows to increase by 2-8 points [20-21]. The alkylation process developed at VNIINeftekhim is carried out in the presence of zeolitic catalysts in the temperature range of 300-450 °C, under a pressure of 5 MPa. At the same time, the process of alkylation of benzene with the participation of propane-propylene fraction was developed by the Ufa State University of Oil and Technology (UNTDU) using a heterogeneous alumina catalyst [22]. The following other technologies of benzene alkylation are also known in the world: "Alkymax" of UOP company and "Katstill" of Lummus company [23].

At this point, it should be emphasized that the use of cheap olefinic gases from the catalytic cracking process in the NQIZ of the alkylation process is economically efficient. In addition, as a result of this process, the amount of benzene decreases, and the total amount of aromatic hydrocarbons increases [10].

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Thus, in order to introduce alkylation units, a large amount of non-aromatic high-octane gasoline component resources must be available.

Figure 1. Technological scheme of the Bensat device of the UOP company

hydrogenation of the benzene- containing fraction of the reformate is based on the hydrogenation of benzene to cyclohexane. Such technologies have been developed by firms such as UOP (BenSat process, Figure 1) and Lummus (Sinsat process). A relatively complex Benfree process was developed by the company Axens, which includes distillation and hydrogenation in the liquid phase in a separate reactor [24].

The hydrogenation process in a solid catalyst bed reactor is carried out at a temperature of 150-300 °C and a pressure of 2.5-3 MPa. A nickel Raney catalyst in the form of a suspension in the reaction mixture acts as a catalyst in the hydrogenation device in the liquid phase. The general disadvantage of benzene hydrogenation devices is the reduction of the octane number by several points.

hydroisomerization of benzene to methylcyclopentane *makes* it possible to

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increase the octane number by several points, while reducing the amount of benzene and the amount of aromatic hydrocarbons in the composition of commercial gasoline [25]. The purpose of this process is to hydrogenate benzene to cyclohexane and then isomerize it to methylcyclopentane, which in the mixed state has a higher octane number than benzene. As a raw material in the "Rigiz" process developed by UNTDU, b.q.h. - 85 °C or b.q.h. A boiler is used in the temperature range of - 115 °C (Fig. 2) [26].

Figure 2. General technological scheme of Rigiz process developed by UNTDU: 1 – reforming device; 2 – rectification column; 3 – hydrogenation reactor; 4 – stabilization column; 5 – gas separator; 6 – heat exchanger; 7 – cooler; 8 – reboiler. I – plowed raw material; II - reformation; III – light fraction of reforming; IV – reforming residual fraction; V – gas containing hydrogen; VI –

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hydrogen gas; VII – stable hydrogenizate; VIII – high-octane gasoline component with improved environmental properties; IX - reflux.

The "Debolk" process was developed by the Olkat company, which is mainly aimed at the development of the K-150B benzene hydroisomerization catalyst [27]. The following analogs of this process have been developed by different companies of the world: "Bensat" by the FIN company, "Penex-Plus" by the UOP company [28].

The main disadvantage of these processes is that the hydroisomerization process cannot be carried out in one reactor due to the release of excess heat as a result of hydrogenation of benzene. This will lead to the use of two or three reactors, thereby increasing the capital and operating costs of the NPP.

From the analysis of the above technologies proposed to reduce the content of aromatic hydrocarbons, especially benzene, in the composition of car gasoline and the production of modern environmentally demanding commodity gasoline products, it can be concluded that the octane number T.U. It is possible to produce gasoline of up to 92 brands. But in order to produce car gasoline with an octane number of 95 or 98, which meets the requirements of the Eurostandard in terms of hydrocarbon content, it is necessary to develop and introduce new technologies.

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